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ADR ASSESSMENT METHODS: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Adverse drug reaction (ADR) is defined as any response to a drug which is harmful and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function. An increased understanding of the prevalence and nature of ADRs, as well as recognition of patients perspectives on quality of life, would enable us as a profession to identify and target specific areas for vigorous pharmaceutical care. It is important to identify the risks for ADRs as they are life threatening, henceforth the common drugs causing ADRs, their therapeutic class, demographic data of patients suffered from ADRs and concomitant medications used should be known. Also, ADR specific data such as type of reaction, system affected and probable causes will be of great help to minimize the ADRs. The process of defining and concluding about ADRs should be continuous and ongoing to keep a record of newly marketed drugs and medicinal products. More over strict drug analyzing, clinical data and in vivo study is also required if feasible. This article focuses on the adverse reaction and its assessment methods.

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INTRODUCTION

Adverse drug reaction (ADR) is defined as “Any response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function”.¹

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADR):

It is a response to drug, which alters the normal physiological function of the body, factors which causes ADR includes mainly multiple drug therapy, age and gender.

There are mainly 2 types of ADR. They are:

TYPE A: These are common, predictable, dose dependent, they are seldom fatal

TYPE B: These are uncommon, unpredictable, dose independent; they involve relatively high rates of serious morbidity.

ADR's may arise as a result of Immunological or non-immunological mechanisms.²

According to Rawlins & Thompson classification, ADRs are defined as type A, type B, type C and type D.³

Type A: In this over enhancement of the normal pharmacology of the medication is predictable and is related to dosage.

Type B: In this type reaction is unrelated to normal pharmacology and unpredictable.

Type C: Reactions include those associated with prolonged therapy e.g. analgesic nephropathy. Type D: Here reactions consist of delayed reactions e.g. carcinogenesis and teratogenesis.

An increased understanding of the prevalence and nature of ADRs, as well as an appreciation of patients perspectives on quality of life, would enable us to identify and target specific areas for vigorous pharmaceutical care. Clinicians often do not recognize drug related problems. Henceforth, it is utmost important to identify the risks of ADRs. The common drugs causing ADRs, their therapeutic class, demographic data of patients suffered from ADRs & concomitant medications used, past history should be known to detect an ADR. Also ADR specific data such as type of reaction, system affected, drug related problems and probable causes will be of great help to minimize the ADRs.¹²

METHODS FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF ADR'S:

The ADR's were assessed for the causality, severity, preventability, and predictability.

Causality criteria

The Naranjo's Algorithm or Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale (Table 1) was used to evaluate the causality relationship between a likely ADR and a drug.¹³ It is a questionnaire form which contains 10 questions with the options yes, no and does not know and for each option, the score will be given. The total score calculated from this questionnaire defines the category as >9: Definite, 5-8: Probable and 1-4: Possible.

TABLE 1: NARANJO ALGORITHM OR ADR'S PROBABILITY SCALE.

SL. NO.	Questionnaires	Yes	No	Do not know	Score
1	Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	1	0	0	
2	Did adverse drug reaction (ADR) appear after the suspected drug was administered?	2	-1	0	
3	Did ADR improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was administered?	1	0	0	
4	Did the adverse reaction appear when the drug was re-administered?	2	-1	0	
5	Are there any alternative causes (other than the drug) that could have caused the reaction?	-1	2	0	
6	Did the reaction reappear when placebo was given?	-1	1	0	
7	Was the drug detected in the blood (or other fluids) in concentration known to be toxic?	1	0	0	
8	Was the ADR more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	1	0	0	
9	Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	1	0	0	
10	Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	1	0	0	
Total score:					

Severity criteria

The severity criteria of the reaction as mild, moderate and severe was determined according to Hartwig Scale *et al.*,¹⁴ as given below (Table 2). Mild ADR's (Level 1, 2) were self-limiting and able to resolve over time without treatment and do not contribute to prolongation of length of stay.

Moderate ADRs (Level 3,4,5) requires therapeutic intervention and hospitalization prolonged by 1 day but it can be resolved in 24 hrs by changing the drug therapy or by giving specific treatment to prevent a further outcome. Severe ADR's (Level 6,7) is life-threatening, as they cause disability and prolonged hospital stay or lead to hospitalization, required intensive medical care or lead to the death of the patient.

TABLE 2: HARTWIG SEVERITY SCALE.

Level 1	An ADR occurred but required no change in treatment with the suspected drug.
Level 2	The ADR required that treatment with the suspected drug be held, discontinued, or otherwise changed. No antidote or other treatment requirement was required No increase in length of stay (LOS)
Level 3	The ADR required that treatment with the suspected drug be held, discontinued, or otherwise changed. AND/OR An antidote or other treatment was required. No increase in length of stay (LOS).
Level 4	(A) Any level 3 ADR which increases the length of stay by at least 1 day. OR (B) The ADR was the reason for the admission.
Level 5	Any level 4 ADR which requires intensive medical care.
Level 6	The adverse reaction caused permanent harm to the patient.
Level 7	The adverse reaction either directly or indirectly led to the death of the patient.

Predictability criteria

The Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) guidelines for preparing core clinical-safety information on drugs adapted the assessment of predictability criteria.¹⁵ Patients who have had the drug on a previous occasion(s): If the drug was previously well-tolerated at the same dose and route of administration, the ADR is *not predictable*; if there was a history of allergy or previous reactions to the drug, the ADR is *predictable*. Patients who have never had the drug previously: Incidence of the ADR reported in product information or other literature determines its predictability (Table 3).

TABLE 3: CRITERIA FOR DETERMINING PREDICTABILITY OF AN ADR's.

SL. No.	Incidence rate	Incidence Description	Predictability
1.	$\geq 1/10$	Very common	Predictable
2.	$\geq 1/100$ and $< 1/10$	Common	Predictable
3.	$\geq 1/1000$ and $< 1/100$	Uncommon	Not predictable
4.	$\geq 1/10,000$ and $< 1/1000$	Rare	Not predictable
5.	$< 1/10,000$	Very rare	Not predictable

Preventability criteria:

The criteria of Schumock and Thornton were modified to assess and categorize ADRs into definitely, probably or not preventable (Table 4).¹⁶ The factor "toxic serum drug level" was omitted from the original criteria, and 2 questions (4 and 5, section B) on the use of preventative measures were added.

TABLE 4: CRITERIA FOR DETERMINING PREVENTABILITY OF AN ADR's - MODIFIED SCHUMOCK AND THORNTON PREVENTABILITY SCALE.

SECTION A
Answering "yes" to one or more of the following implies that an ADR is DEFINITELY preventable.
1. Was there a history of allergy or previous reactions to the drug?
2. Was the drug involved inappropriate for the patient's clinical condition?
3. Was the dose, route, or frequency of administration inappropriate for the patient's age, weight, or disease state? <i>If answers are all negative to the above, then proceed to Section B</i>
SECTION B
Answering "yes" to one or more of the following implies that an ADR is PROBABLY preventable
1. Was required therapeutic drug monitoring or other necessary laboratory tests not performed?
2. Was a documented drug interaction involved in the ADR?
3. Was poor compliance involved in the ADR?
4. Was a preventative measure not administered to the patient?
5. If a preventative measure was administered, was it inadequate and/or inappropriate? Answer 'NO' if this question is nonapplicable.
<i>If answers are all negative to the above, then proceed to Section C</i>
SECTION C
The ADR is NOT preventable

CONCLUSION

The process of defining and concluding about ADRs should be continuous and ongoing to keep a record of newly marketed drugs and medicinal products. Moreover strict drug analyzing and in vivo study is also required if feasible. To determine the likely relationship between the drug and the adverse drug reaction the assessment scale is used. Casualty assessment scales used to determine the ADRs not only helps to identify the ADRs its probability and severity but also it helps to identify the risk occurred and to upgrade the quality of life of the patient by overcoming the risk with suitable therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Requirements for adverse reaction reporting. Geneva, Switzerland: world health organization; 1975.
2. Parker CW. Allergic reactions in man. *Pharmacol Rev* 1983;34:85-194.
3. Rawlins MD, Thompson JW, Davies DM. Pathogenesis of adverse drug reactions. *Textbook of adverse drug reactions*. Oxford University Press 1977;10.
4. Bates D, Leape L, Petrycki S. Incidence and preventability of adverse drug events in hospitalized adults. *J Gen Intern Med* 1993; 8:289-294.
5. Dormann H, Muth-Selbach U, Krebs S. Incidence and costs of adverse drug reactions during hospitalization: computerized monitoring versus stimulated spontaneous reporting. *Drug safety* 2000; 22:161-168.
6. Mjorndal T, Boman MD, Hagg S. adverse drug reactions as a cause for admissions to a department of internal medicine. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*2002; 11:65 – 72.
7. Tegeder I, Levy M, Muth-Selbach U. Retrospective analysis of the frequency and recognition of adverse drug reactions by means of automatically recorded laboratory signals. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 1999; 47:557 – 564.
8. White TJ, Arakelian A, Rho JP. Counting the costs of drug-related adverse events. *Pharmacoeconomics* 1999; 15:445 - 458.
9. Roughead EE, Gilbert AL, Primrose JG, Sansom LN. Drug-related hospital admissions: a review of Australian studies published 1988-1996. *Medi J Aust*1998; 168:405 - 408.
10. National hospital morbidity data collection - Australia (excluding NT) (1992-1993)
11. Wilson R, Runciman W, Gibberd R. Quality in Australian health care study. *Med J Aust*1995; 163:458 - 471.
12. Wenchen K W, Nicholas P. Evaluation of outpatient adverse drug reactions leading to hospitalization. *Am J Health Syst Pharma* 2003;60:251-254.
13. Naranjo, C.A. Busto, U Sellers, E.M. Sandor, P. Ruiz, I. Roberts, E.A. Janecek, E. Domecq, C. Greenblatt, D.J. A method for estimating the probability of adverse drug reactions. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*1981; 80: 289 - 295.
14. Hartwig, S.C. Siegel, J. Schneider, P.J. Preventability and severity assessment in reporting adverse drug reactions. *Am J Hosp Pharm* 1992; 49: 2229 - 2232.
15. Council for International Organization for Medical Science (CIOMS) (1994) WGI, guidelines for preparing core clinical-safety information on drugs. Council for International Organization For Medical Sciences, Geneva.
16. Schumock G, Thornton J. Focusing on the preventability of adverse drug reactions. *Hosp Pharm* 1992; 27:538.

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